

1 **TECTONIC CONTROL ON SEDIMENTARY DYNAMICS IN INTRAPLATE OCEANIC SETTINGS: A**
2 **GEOMORPHOLOGICAL IMAGE OF THE EASTERN CANARY BASIN AND INSIGHTS ON ITS MIDDLE-UPPER**
3 **MIOCENE TO QUATERNARY VOLCANO-TECTONIC-SEDIMENTARY EVOLUTION**

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10 **ABSTRACT**

11 **This paper integrates sedimentary, tectonic and volcanic geological processes inside a model of volcano-**
12 **tectonic activity in oceanic intraplate domains related to rifted continental margins. The study case, the**
13 **eastern Canary Basin (NE Atlantic), is one of the few places in the world where giant MDTs and**
14 **Quaternary volcanic and hydrothermal edifices take place in intraplate domains. In this paper, we analyse**
15 **how two structural systems (WNW-ESE and NNE-SSW) matching with the oceanic fabric control the**
16 **location of volcanic systems, seafloor tectonic reliefs and subsequently the distribution of main**
17 **sedimentary systems. Linear turbidite channels, debris flow lobes and the lateral continuity of structural**
18 **and volcanic reliefs follow a WNW-ESE trend matching the tracks of the oceanic fracture zones.**
19 **Furthermore, escarpments, anticline axes and volcanic ridges follow a NNE-SSW trend matching normal**
20 **faults delimiting blocks of oceanic basement. The morpho-structural analysis of all the above**
21 **geomorphological features shows evidence of a volcanic and tectonic activity from the middle–upper**
22 **Miocene to the Lower–Middle Pleistocene spread over the whole of the eastern Canary Basin that**
23 **reached the western Canary Islands. This reactivation changes the paradigm in the seamount province of**
24 **Canary Islands reported inactive since Cretaceous. A tecto-sedimentary model is proposed for this period**
25 **of time that can be applied in other intraplate domains of the world. A tectonic uplift in the study area**

26 with a thermal anomaly triggered volcanic and hydrothermal activity and the subsequent flank collapse
27 and emplacement of mass transport deposits on the Western Canary Slope. Furthermore, this uplift
28 reactivated the normal basement faults, both trending WNW-ESE and NNE-SSW, generating folds and
29 faults that control the location of turbidite channels, escarpments, mass transport deposits and volcanic
30 edifices.

31 **Keywords:** Canary Basin, geomorphology, tectonics, oceanic fracture zones

32

33 1. INTRODUCTION

34 Deep seafloor areas are poorly surveyed. In the last decade, the high-resolution geological knowledge
35 of deep-water areas in oceanic intraplate domains have been the objective for several researches focused
36 on geohazards (Geersen et al., 2015), critical metallic elements (Marino et al., 2017), energy resources (e.g.
37 H₂ and hydrocarbons; Dabson et al., 2016) and fragile extremophile chemosynthetic ecosystems (Hensen
38 et al., 2015).

39 MTDs have been intensively studied in deep-waters as geohazards (Harbitz et al., 2006) and energy
40 reservoirs and stores (Cox et al., 2020; Madrussani et al., 2018). Giant submarine landslides sourced in
41 continental areas are often channelled to the adjacent oceanic seafloor areas as in the Bay of Bengal (Curry
42 et al., 2002), the Norwegian margin (Evans et al., 2005), Canary Islands (Hunt and Jarvis, 2017; León et al.,
43 2019) and the northwest African margin (Krastel et al., 2019). In the case of the Bay of Bengal, oceanic
44 fracture zones control dynamic and location of MDTs in the oceanic domain (Levchenko and Verzhbitskii,
45 2005). In volcanic ocean islands, periods of intense volcanic activity have been proposed as the most
46 important mechanism generating main flank collapses (Hunt et al., 2014; Hunt and Jarvis, 2017; León et al.,
47 2019). These processes, generally generated on land along huge headwall escarpments, have effects
48 downslope generating complexes of debris avalanche/flow deposits as well as turbidite deposits on the

49 abyssal plains (Brunet et al., 2016; Hunt and Jarvis, 2017; León et al., 2019; Masson et al., 2002, 1998;
50 Urgeles et al., 1999).

51 In oceanic intraplate domains, normal and reverse high-angle faults and folds have been associated to
52 the reactivation of oceanic fracture zones creating associated seafloor reliefs. For example, blocks of normal
53 faults (Basile and Mascle, 1990) and transpressional features (Davison et al., 2016) related to the Romanche
54 Fracture Zone have been observed, as well as reverse faults and folds in relation to oceanic fractures zones
55 in the Indian Ocean (Bull, 1990; Curray and Munasinghe, 1989).

56 The differential rheological behaviour of the lithosphere related to thickness changes (Patriat and
57 Labails, 2006) and magmatism, together with the subsequent hydrothermal activity (Medialdea et al.,
58 2017), have also been invoked as a mechanism that can produce diapirism-like structures, doming, folding
59 and faulting in these oceanic intraplate environments.

60 Structural inheritance in oceanic lithosphere control the style, orientation, and location of oceanic
61 intraplate volcanism (e.g. Tasman Sea – East Australia; Richards et al., 2018). Besides in Wharton Basin
62 (Indian Ocean), high magnitude earthquakes (>8) and subsequent tsunamis are also related with structural
63 oceanic inheritance, in particular left-lateral strike-slip reactivation of existing oceanic fracture zones
64 (Geersen et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2017a).

65 Oceanic fracture zones open and sustain fluid flow pathways from lithospheric mantle to the overlying
66 sediments, and the subsequent generation of energy resources by the accumulation of CH₄ and H₂ due to
67 serpentinization processes (Hensen et al., 2019). In deep-waters, this fluid flow sustains over seafloor fragile
68 extremophile chemosynthetic ecosystems (Kelley et al., 2001).

69 The eastern Canary Basin is one of the few places in the world where to study in the Quaternary the
70 interaction and relationship among volcanism, tectonic and giant submarine landslide. Here, an intensive
71 research has been carried out in fields such as the Quaternary or current volcanic and hydrothermal activity
72 (Klügel et al., 2011; Van den Bogaard, 2013; Medialdea et al., 2017; Somoza et al., 2017), gravitational

73 instabilities and mass-transport deposits (MTDs) (Georgiopoulou et al., 2009, 2010; Hunt et al., 2011, 2013,
74 2014; Palomino et al., 2016; León et al., 2019), the relationship between MTDs and volcanic activity (Hunt
75 et al., 2014; Hunt and Jarvis, 2017; León et al., 2019) and the presence of critical metallic elements (Marino
76 et al., 2017). However, only a few of these studies have focused on the relationship between tectonics,
77 volcanic activity and seafloor morphology (Medialdea et al., 2017; Sánchez-Guillamón et al., 2018b, 2018a).

78 The main objective of this paper is to integrate sedimentary, tectonic and volcanic geological processes
79 inside a model of volcano-tectonic activity in oceanic intraplate domains. The paper describes the main
80 geomorphological features in a wide area to the west of the Canary Islands and to the east of the Madeira
81 Abyssal Plain, and reveals two main highlights; (i) The structural inheritance control of the oceanic fabric in
82 the location of volcanic systems, seafloor tectonic reliefs and subsequently the main sedimentary bodies;
83 and (ii) The volcanic and tectonic activity from the middle–upper Miocene to the Lower–Middle Pleistocene
84 in the study area conducted/controlled by the reactivation of oceanic fracture zones.

85 The nature of the volcanic and tectonic reliefs and the timing of MTDs and its relationship with the main
86 tectonic features, has an important bearing on our understanding of the Cenozoic volcano-tectonic and
87 sedimentary dynamic in this area. In particular, because the seamount province of southern Canary Island
88 Volcanic Province (CIVP) have been reported as inactive since the Cretaceous (van den Bogaard, 2013). A
89 tecto-sedimentary model is proposed for this period of time that can be applied in other intraplate domains
90 of the world, where tectonic uplift, volcanic/hydrothermal activity and the subsequent flank collapse and
91 emplacement of mass transport deposits could take place.

92

93 **2. GEOLOGICAL SETTING**

94 The Canary Basin is an extensive area in the eastern Central Atlantic located to the east of the Great
95 Meteor seamounts, to the south of the Madeira-Tore Rise and to the north of the Cape Verde Rise (Fig. 1A)
96 (Rothwell et al., 1998). It comprises the Madeira and Canary Islands and a 1,500 km segment of the
97 northwest African margin (Fig. 1A). This area plunges westward to the Madeira and Cabo Verde abyssal

98 plains, dropping down to 5,400 m water depth (mwd) along a smooth continental slope of $\sim 0.1^\circ$ (Palomino
99 et al., 2016).

100 The eastern Canary Basin, with a sediment thickness of up to 2 s two-way travel time (TWT), lies on an
101 oceanic crust of Aptian age (120 Ma; Ranero et al., 1997). The magnetic anomalies derived from the Atlantic
102 spreading fabric outline a regional trend of WNW-ESE oceanic fracture zones (Klitgord and Schouten, 1986;
103 Roest et al., 1992) with depressions and highs. Numerous volcanic seamounts related to recent magmatic
104 and hydrothermal activity are reported on the Western Canary Slope (WCS) and the distal part of the
105 Madeira Distributary Channel System (MDCS) (Fig. 1B) (Medialdea et al., 2017; Sánchez-Guillamón et al.,
106 2018a, 2018b).

107 The CIVP is a NE-SW ridge (ca. 1,500 km long) of volcanic islands and seamounts located approximately
108 300 km to the west of the African continental margin between 23°N and 33°N and forming an archipelago
109 (Fig. 1A). The origin of the Canary archipelago is debatable, but it is widely accepted that the volcanic
110 edifices resulted from a mantle plume upwelling close to the northwest African continental margin. The
111 dynamics of this mantle plume generated lithospheric melting periods of active volcanism from the Jurassic
112 to the present (van den Bogaard, 2013). A rough age evolution can be observed from the oldest seamount,
113 Lars, located in the NE of the ridge (68 Ma) to the recent events in the western part of the ridge in La Palma
114 (2021 and 1971) and El Hierro (2011) islands (Geldmacher et al., 2005).

115 It should be noted that in the last 15 Ma the emersion of the westernmost volcanic buildings of the
116 Canary Islands has taken place (Carracedo and Troll, 2016). This factor together with the eruptions in these
117 volcanic buildings favour the development of mass transport deposits on the continental slope in relation
118 to the seismic-volcanic activity generated during the eruptive processes (León et al., 2019).

119 This long tectonic history has built specific geomorphological features and domains in the eastern
120 Canary Basin, which is characterized by two main geomorphological features: (i) the smooth nature of its
121 slope gradient (0.1° - 6°) and the presence of large MTDs coming from the CIVP and the African continental
122 margin (Hunt et al., 2014, 2013; Krastel et al., 2001; León et al., 2019; Masson et al., 2002, 1998; Talling et

123 al., 2007; Urgeles et al., 2001; Wynn et al., 2000); and (ii) the presence of seamounts (>1,000 m high; IHO,
124 2013), hills (<1,000 m high; IHO, 2013) and mounds (<500 m high; IHO, 2013), on a seafloor with slopes of
125 up to 25° (Medialdea et al., 2017; Palomino et al., 2016; Sánchez-Guillamón et al., 2018b; van den Bogaard,
126 2013) (Fig. 1B).

127 Some authors proposed that intraplate deformation of the oceanic lithosphere results from the
128 reactivation of the oceanic fracture zones due to changes in the plate boundary stresses between Nubia
129 and Eurasia (Mantovani et al., 2007). To explain errors in the previous kinematic models, the same authors
130 propose a model with two subplates in this boundary, Iberia and Morocco, the latter extending between
131 the Gloria transform fault to the north and the Atlantis oceanic fracture zone to the south, which would
132 pass eastward between the islands of Tenerife and Gran Canaria (Mantovani et al., 2007) (Fig. 1A). The
133 activity of this fracture zone has been used by other authors to explain the state of stresses in the region
134 (Geyer et al., 2016), as well as the regional deformation obtained from the analysis of time series with
135 Global Navigation Satellite Stations System (Arnosó et al., 2020; Barbero et al., 2021).

136

137 3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

138 An extensive geophysical dataset (Fig. 1C) acquired between 1999 and 2013 (Table 1) onboard the BIO
139 *Hespérides*, the R/V *Miguel de Oliver* and the R/V *Sarmiento de Gamboa* is analysed in the present paper.
140 This dataset was acquired to support the proposal submitted by Spain to the Commission on the Limits of
141 the Continental Shelf (United Nations) named “Partial Submission of Data and Information on the Limits of
142 the Continental Shelf of Spain to the West of the Canary Islands, pursuant to Part VI and Annex II of United
143 Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea”
144 (https://www.un.org/Depts/los/clcs_new/submissions_files/submission_esp_77_2014.htm). The Spanish
145 Foreign Office (Ministerio de Asuntos Exteriores de España – MAEC) classified this dataset, except the Leg
146 SUBVENT1 (white dot line in Fig. 1C) of the SUBVENT1-MAEC cruise (Vázquez et al., 2013), as “restricted”.

Year	Oceanographic cruise	Research vessel	Methods	Equipment description	Availability	Metadata / cruise report
1999	ZEEE_1999 29HE19990516	Hespérides	MBES VHR	Kongsberg-Simrad EM-12 TOPAS	Restricted	https://doi.org/10.20351/29he19990516
2000	ZEEE_2000 29HE20000906	Hespérides	MBES VHR	Kongsberg-Simrad EM-12 TOPAS	Restricted	https://doi.org/10.20351/29he20000906
2010	GAROE_2010 29HE20100802	Hespérides	MBES VHR	Kongsberg-Simrad EM-120 TOPAS PS-18	Restricted	https://doi.org/10.20351/29he20100802 Cruise Report: Somoza et al., 2011a
2011	DRAGO_0511	Miguel Oliver	MBES VHR	Kongsberg-Simrad EM-302 TOPAS PS-18	Restricted	http://hdl.handle.net/10508/451 Cruise Report: Vázquez et al., 2011
2011	ZEEE_2011 29HE20110810	Hespérides	MBES VHR	Kongsberg-Simrad EM-120 TOPAS PS-18	Restricted	https://doi.org/10.20351/29he20110810
2011	GAIRE_2011 29SG20111126	Sarmiento de Gamboa	MCS MBES VHR	Guns capacity: 4,600 inch ³ (75.38 l). Streamer: 3,500 m long & 280 channels Atlas HYDROSWEEEP DS Atlas PARASOUND P-35	Restricted	https://doi.org/10.20351/29sg20111126 Cruise Report: Somoza et al., 2011b
2012	AMULEY_2012 29HE20120507	Hespérides	MBES VHR	Kongsberg-Simrad EM-120 TOPAS PS-18	Restricted	https://doi.org/10.20351/29he20120507
2012	ZEEE_2012 29HE20120620	Hespérides	MBES VHR	Kongsberg-Simrad EM-120 TOPAS PS-18	Restricted	https://doi.org/10.20351/29he20120620
2013	SUBVENT1- MAEC_2013	Hespérides	MBES VHR	Kongsberg-Simrad EM-120 TOPAS PS-18	Leg SUBVENT1 By request	https://doi.org/10.20351/29he20130921 Cruise Report: Vázquez et al., 2013

148

149 **Table 1.-** Summary of methods and oceanographic cruises used in the present paper. MCS, multichannel seismic; MBES,
150 multibeam echosounder; TOPAS, topographic parametric sonar; VHR, very high-resolution parametric profiles.

151

152 A total of 440,000 km² have been covered with multibeam echosounder (MBES) (bathymetry and
153 backscatter) data on board the BIO *Hespérides* (Kongsberg-Simrad EM-12, EM-120), the R/V *Miguel Oliver*
154 (Kongsberg-Simrad EM-302) and the R/V *Sarmiento de Gamboa* (Atlas HYDROSWEEEP DS). The operational
155 parameters are summarized in **Table 2**.

156

<i>MBES system</i>	<i>Research vessel</i>	<i>Cruises</i>	λ	<i>Navigation system</i>	<i>Beams</i>	<i>Angular cover</i>	<i>H. resolution</i>	<i>V. resolution</i>
SIMRAD EM-12	<i>Hespérides</i>	ZEEE_1999 ZEEE_2000	13 kHz	Seapath 200	127	120°	2° x 2°	0.6 m
SIMRAD EM-120	<i>Hespérides</i>	GAROE_2010 ZEEE_2011 ZEEE_2012 AMULEY_2012 SUBVENT1- MAEC_2013	13 kHz	Seapath 200	191	150°	2° x 1°	0.1 – 0.4 m
SIMRAD EM-302	<i>Miguel Oliver</i>	DRAGO_2011	30 kHz	Seapath 200	432	150°	1° x 1°	~0.4 – 1 m
ATLAS DS Hydrosweep	<i>Sarmiento de Gamboa</i>	GAIRE_2011	15 kHz	Applanix PosMV	345	140°	1° x 1°	0.06 m

158

159 **Table 2.-** Summary of multibeam system parameters used in the present paper. λ , frequency; H. resolution, horizontal resolution;
160 V. resolution, vertical resolution.

161

162 Very high-resolution (VHR) profiles were recorded with chirp parametric source TOPAS PS-18 (BIO
163 *Hespérides* and R/V *Miguel de Oliver*) and Atlas PARASOUND P-35 (R/V *Sarmiento de Gamboa*) with a total
164 of 65,800 km acquired. TOPAS PS-18 and Atlas PARASOUND P-35 worked in CHIRP mode, shooting each 4
165 to 10 s and with a secondary lower frequency of 1.5 to 5 kHz and 3.5 to 5 kHz, respectively. Both systems
166 provided a maximum penetration of 150 ms with a resolution of 0.5 to 1 m.

167 Multichannel seismic (MCS) profiles were acquired during the GAIRE_2011 cruise. The configuration of
168 the seismic system consisted of two arrays of airguns with a total capacity of 75 L shooting every 50 m and
169 a 3,500-m-long Sentinel digital streamer with 280 channels.

170 Bathymetry and backscatter of MBES raw data were processed with CARIS HIPS and SIPS software.
171 Bathymetry models and backscatter mosaics were produced at 150 m and ca. 56 m resolution. After
172 processing, the mosaics were integrated in an ArcGIS database for further analysis. IHS KINGDOM TM
173 software was used to interpret the VHR and MCS seismic profiles.

174 Finally, data from free public databases regarding the free-air gravity anomalies from
175 https://topex.ucsd.edu/cgi-bin/get_data.cgi (Sandwell et al., 2013, 2014; Sandwell and Smith, 2009), total
176 field magnetic anomalies from the World Digital Magnetic Anomaly Map (WDMAM; <http://wdmam.org/>)
177 and the oceanic fabric (Global Seafloor Fabrics database; <http://www.soest.hawaii.edu/PT/GSFML/>;
178 [Matthews et al., 2011; Wessel et al., 2015]) were taken into account for mapping the oceanic fracture
179 zones.

180

181

182 4. GEOMORPHOLOGICAL DOMAINS

183 Four geomorphological domains were studied in the eastern Canary Basin: the Madeira Distributary
184 Channel System (MDCS), the Western Canary Debris Flow System (WCDFS), the Western Canary Slope
185 (WCS) and the southern Canary Island Volcanic Province (CIVP) (Fig. 1B).

186 The MDCS is located to the north of the eastern Canary Basin from 4,800 to 5,400 mwd and from
187 $32^{\circ}30'N/23^{\circ}30'W$ to $30^{\circ}N/20^{\circ}30'W$. The study area is located in the distal part of the MDCS (Fig. 1B). Here,
188 this geomorphological domain is characterized by the presence of a complex turbidite channel system
189 (turbidite lobes and linear channels) (Fig. 2A and 2B) with a very smooth relief (0.02° - 0.016° in slope
190 gradient; Fig. 2C) and volcanic edifices (Fig 2B) with higher slope gradient values (see mounds and hills in
191 Table 3).

192 The WCDFS is widely extended from 3,800 to 5,400 mwd. Two main areas have been differentiated: the
193 northern and southern systems (Fig. 1B). These systems are differentiated in their sourcing areas and the
194 southern one is mainly buried. They constitute six connected branches (I - VI in Fig. 1B) building a vast buried
195 seismic unit characterized by transparent acoustic seismic facies of more than 200,000 km². The northern
196 system extends from the west of the westernmost Canary Islands (the base of La Palma and El Hierro
197 islands) to the Madeira Abyssal Plain; the southern system, with undetermined south and east limits,
198 extends ca. 350 km to the west from the southern CIVP (The Paps and Tropic seamounts) (Fig. 1B).

199 The WCS stretches between 4,800 and 5,400 mwd to the south of the MDCS and to the west of the
200 WCDFS (Fig. 1B). It is characterized by the presence of a very smooth general slope gradient of 0.04° to
201 0.15° , broken locally by volcanic reliefs and terraced by structural lineaments (Fig. 3).

202 In the study area, the southern CIVP is constrained between 3,600 and 4,700 mwd, only exceeded by
203 the top of the main seamounts (Fig. 3). It is located to the southwest of the Canary Islands archipelago (from

204 27.2°N/18.5°W to 23.5°N/21.7°W) and comprises volcanic reliefs such as seamounts, mounds and hills (Fig.
205 1).

206 The geomorphological features of the above geomorphological domains are described below.

207

208 5. GEOMORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES

209 5.1. Turbidite channels

210 Turbidite channels have been recognized mainly in the MDCS and WCDFS (Figs. 2 and 3).

211 5.1.1. Turbidite channels in the Madeira Distributary Channel System

212 In the MDCS, the turbidite channels constitute a linear system (Fig. 2). The network of turbidite channels
213 deepens towards the northwest, showing a low degree of sinuosity and two main directions. A main WNW-
214 ESE linear pathway with a high lateral continuity of about 150 to 250 km length follows the same direction
215 as the local oceanic fracture zones (red dot lines in Fig. 2B). These oceanic fracture zones were mapped
216 taking into account the free-air gravity anomalies and total field magnetic anomalies. The WNW-ESE linear
217 pathway is connected to another secondary network running NW-SE (black arrow in Fig. 2B) and WSW-ESE
218 (grey arrow in Fig. 2B) of 10 to 40 km in length. This system of turbidite channels shows steep wall profiles
219 with a slope of up to 7°, a width ranging from 800 to 1,500 m and incisions ranging from 20 to 50 m in depth
220 (Figs. 4A and 4C).

221 Volcanic edifices contribute to the diverse separation of the channels from each other, bringing some
222 of them as close as 5 km or splitting them apart by more than 30 km (Figs. 3 and 4C).

223 5.1.2. Turbidite channels in the Western Canary Debris Flow System

224 In the north of the WCDFS, turbidite channels are located in the proximal parts of the different branches
225 (Fig. 3). In branches I and II, two networks of turbidite channels were observed (Figs. 3, 4D and 4E). The first
226 network is composed of channels ranging from 1.5 to 5.5 m in braided at the surface of the debris flow

227 deposits, giving them a moderate backscatter (“i” in Fig. 4D). The second network (“ch” in Fig. 4D) is larger
228 than the first one. In the proximal area, these lineal and non-braided channels ranges from 13 to 20 m in
229 depth, from 10 to 50 km in length and from 0.6 to 8 km in width. Downslope, the channels measure up to
230 300 km in length and 50 to 70 m in depth (Figs. 2 and 3). The two channel networks follow a NW-SE direction
231 (Figs. 3 and 4D) and change sharply to the WNW-ESE at 30°N (~4,850 mwd) in the vicinity of the MDCS,
232 matching the tracks of oceanic fractures. Here, in the distal part of branches I and II, turbidite channels
233 follow a narrow linear track 1 km in width and 25 m in depth, similar to that found in the MDCS.

234 In branches III and IV, turbidite channels source from the base of the El Julian debris avalanche, and
235 compose a linear and discontinuous NW-SE set of turbidite channels 30 to 50 km long and 1.5 to 3.8 km
236 wide (Fig. 3). The channels direction change sharply, to W-E at ca. 28° 30’N (~4,450 mwd) in branch III and
237 ca. 27° 45’N (~4,250 mwd) in branch IV, approximately matching the tracks of the oceanic fracture zones.
238 The middle sector of branch IV is incised by W-E turbidite channels ranging from 20 to 80 km in length, 1 to
239 7 km in width and 8 to 10 m in depth, and is characterized by a moderate to low backscatter strength (“ch”
240 in Fig. 5D and 6).

241

242 5.2. Lobes of mass-transport deposits

243 Two types of MTDs were observed in the study area: fan-shaped lobes and elongated lobes.

244 5.2.1. Fan-shaped lobes of MTDs

245 Fan-shaped lobes (FSLs) of MTDs were observed in the MDCS and WCDFS.

246 In the MDCS, thin FSLs of MTDs occur in the distal part of the buried deposits of the WCDFS (Fig. 2B, 4B
247 and 4C) at the end of turbidite channels. They show a thickness of 3 to 5 ms TWT and medium to high
248 backscatter values. They usually fill tectonic depressions such as syncline folding affecting the seafloor (Figs.
249 4B and 4C). Locally, at the end of the thin FSLs, narrow channels start matching the smooth increase in the

250 seafloor slope gradient (Fig. 2C). These channels (evolved from the FSLs) with smooth wall profiles range
251 from 15 to 60 km in length and from 4 to 10 m in depth, and sometimes merge together where the seafloor
252 flattens.

253 In the WCDFS, FSLs of MTDs were observed in the middle part of branch III (Figs. 5D and 5E) and the
254 distal part of branch IV (Figs. 6A and 6B). In branch III, the thin FSLs of MTDs are 3 to 5 ms TWT thick and
255 have a positive relief and medium-high seafloor backscatter strength (Fig. 5D). FSLs were recognized on
256 both sides of the branch, showing a terraced profile and over-topping the wide channel. On the northern
257 side, the FSLs are well developed, configuring elongated and narrow lobes 100 to 170 km long and 5 to 10
258 km wide with a clear NW-SE sedimentary pathway ("1" in Fig. 3). By contrast, in the distal part of branch IV,
259 the thin FSLs of MTDs establish several radial and ramified flows ("fsl" in Figs. 6A and 6B) from 3 to 5 km in
260 width and 25 to 78 km in length, infilling a tectonic depression resulting from vertical faults and smooth
261 folds.

262

263 5.2.2. Elongated lobes of mass-transport deposits

264 The elongated lobes of the MTDs are only represented in the WCDFS. In the northern system, the recent
265 events have been defined as debrites, in particular in branches I, II (Canary Debris Flow; Masson et al., 2002,
266 1998) and IV (Saharian Debris Flow; Gee et al., 1999; Wynn et al., 2000).

267 *The northern system*

268 In the northern system of the WCDFS, VHR parametric profiles and backscatter mosaic show this
269 geomorphological feature as vertically stacked, lengthened lobate bodies with positive relief (Figs. 4E and
270 6), a high to moderate seafloor backscatter strength (Figs. 5A, 5D and 6A) and transparent acoustic seismic
271 facies of 3 to 15 ms TWT in thickness (Figs. 4, 5 and 6) interbedded with high-amplitude reflections in the

272 lateral areas of the branches (Figs. 4E and 5B). Buried events are observed in the lateral and distal areas of
273 the branches. The younger events are located between 4 and 11 ms TWT bsf (Figs. 5 and 6).

274 The northern system of the WCDFS shows a sharp change in direction, from NW-SE to WNW-ESE in
275 branch II and from NW-SE to E-W in branches III and IV. This change in direction marks the transition
276 between the middle and distal sectors in branch II (at ~4,850 mwd), and between the proximal and middle
277 sectors in branches III and IV (at ~4,450 and ~4,300 mwd, respectively) matching the tracks of oceanic
278 fracture zones (Figs. 2 and 3) and covering a tectonically depressed area (Figs. 4E and 6D).

279 In the proximal sector, MTDs incised by turbidite channels fill wide NW-SE valleys (see subsection 5.1.2).
280 Branches I, II and III form a complex mainly sourced from the base of El Hierro and La Palma islands with a
281 NW-SE direction (Figs. 2 and 3). The middle and distal sectors of branches III and IV are located over wide
282 valleys (15-35 km wide) (Fig. 5E) controlled by smooth monoclinical synforms (Fig. 6D) and vertical faults
283 (Figs. 5B, 5E and 6B) deep-rooted in the acoustic basement (Fig. 5C). The distal sectors are characterized by
284 a ramified system of MTDs and radial flow of FSLs controlled by vertical faults and folds (Fig. 6A).

285 *The southern system*

286 The southern system is mostly buried at a depth ranging from 8 to 22 ms TWT bsf (Figs. 7 and 8) and
287 extends more than 400 km in a NW direction from the seamounts of the southern CIVP (Fig. 1A). Recent
288 MTDs (on the seafloor) were detected as small and local lobes in the base of the Echo (Fig. 7D) and The
289 Paps (Fig. 7C) seamounts.

290 Branch V is circumscribed to the Drago, Ico, The Paps and Echo seamounts and the San Borondón crest. To
291 the north of the NW-SE lineation defined by the Ico, The Paps and Echo seamounts, branch V is not
292 detected, but to the southwest of this lineation it is well represented. The lobes of MTDs show an elongated
293 shape (up to 200 km in total length and 50-75 km in width) and a thickness of about 35 ms TWT of
294 transparent acoustic facies. An undetermined quantity of sediments seems to come from the east of the
295 southern CIVP (African continental margin) along surficial channels and a few thin MTDs. The San Borondón

296 crest is located to the southeast of branch V. It is NE-SW oriented over a very smooth (0.5°-1° in slope
297 gradient) domal structure ca. 50 km in diameter. On the western flank, several gravitational instabilities
298 were mapped (Fig. 7A). The southern and eastern boundaries of branch VI were not defined and,
299 consequently, source area of branch VI was not determined with precision although it seems to be mainly
300 located on the African continental margin and, in part, on the Tropic seamount. Branch VI fills highly faulted
301 tectonic depressions (Fig.8A and 8C). Locally, vertical faults offset the seafloor (Fig. 8C). This deformation
302 draws stepped terraces of debrites. The MTDs lie on erosion surfaces (“disc” in Fig. 8) and are affected by
303 fluid migration (veins of blanking acoustic facies in Fig. 8A).

304

305 5.3. Structural lineaments

306 The lineaments in the study area were mapped using bathymetry, backscatter and VHR parametric
307 profiles (Fig. 9). These lineaments were interpreted as structural reliefs. They appear as clusters of NNE-
308 SSW positive reliefs aligned along a sub-parallel anticlines and synclines, and normal faults (Fig. 10).

309 At least five areas (“i” in Fig. 11A) were identified with structural reliefs separated by perpendicular
310 stripes. The stripes match oceanic fracture zones cutting the lateral continuity of these NNE-SSW striking
311 clusters of lineaments.

312 We differentiate linear ridges and escarpments.

313 5.3.1. Linear ridges

314 At least 96 linear ridges were recognized with a N30E mean trend (Fig. 11D) and an average length of
315 14.8 km (between 3.2 and 70 km). They correspond to the anticline’s hinges (Fig. 10D). The folds are both
316 symmetrical and asymmetrical monoclines. The ridges are 10-20 m-high but 5-60 m-high locally. Their
317 wavelength varies between 5 and 20 km-large, but can reach 50 km-large, corresponding in this case to the

318 main antiforms where secondary minor (2-5 km) anticlines (“sa” in Fig. 10D) and synclines are traced over
319 the large ones (“la” in Fig. 10D).

320 Crestal and lateral normal faults cut the anticlines. Reverse faults are scarce. Normal faults (Fig. 10E)
321 occasionally produce minor graben-like structures (“gr” in Fig. 10), anticlines and synthetic fault systems
322 (“sf” in Fig. 10E) with the same downthrown sense. The sub-vertical reverse faults are especially pronounced
323 in several cases, producing small out-of-sequence anticlines and related ridges on the seafloor (Fig. 10A).

324 Acoustic blanking seismic facies at ~20-30 ms TWT are frequent down the axes of the main anticlines,
325 and vertical columns of attenuated amplitude usually appear at the top of the blanking acoustic seismic
326 facies connecting these buried areas with the seafloor and locally with positive reliefs (“bf” in Figs. 9 and
327 10). These buried blanking acoustic seismic facies show a surficial response giving NNE-SSW stripes of low
328 seafloor backscatter (Fig. 9A; see also section 5.1.1.).

329 The synclinal structures are controlled by sub-vertical faults and show seismic onlap reflections (yellow
330 arrows in Figs. 10B and 10C). Sometimes these depressions comprise short valleys, 7 to 15 km in length,
331 perpendicular to the main direction of the slope (“v” in Figs. 9 and 10C). The seafloor backscatter mosaic
332 shows NNE-SSW stripes of low reflectivity on the track of these structures (“bf” in Fig. 9). In the VHR
333 parametric profiles, these features appear over monoclinical folds, sometimes faulted, reflecting buried
334 structures deformed by folds.

335 5.3.2. Escarpments

336 The seafloor in this area is characterized by a great diversity of escarpment types. A total of 349 features
337 were considered, generated by normal faults, monoclines and upwards-attenuated deformation on buried
338 or semi-buried anticlines affected by sub-vertical faults. A single scarp can comprise different origins. The
339 mean trend of these features is N30E (Fig. 11D) and they have an average length of 11.5 km (between 0.7
340 and 62 km), in both cases similar to the ridge values. The height of the escarpments also shows great variety:

341 their minimum and maximum values are 5 and 40 m-high, respectively, with the most frequent values being
342 between 10 and 30 m-high.

343 The escarpments are mainly located in the western part of WCS. They draw a NNE-SSW-oriented
344 terraced terrain where two to four successive levels of stepped terraces can be differentiated (Fig. 10B),
345 ranging from 4,840 to 5,040 mwd. On the other hand, the western part of this sector reaches depths of up
346 to 5,400 mwd in the northern part and 5,200 mwd in the southern part, the bottom surface being
347 characterized by a wavy morphology and a sloping seafloor dominated by smooth anticlinal ridges (Figs. 9B
348 and 10B).

349 In the MCS profiles (Fig. 10D), the sedimentary cover shows intense deformation by folding and faulting
350 deep rooted in the basement structure. The anticlines are usually asymmetrical, with the steeper flanks
351 directed seaward, and hinge axes located on the basement ridges while the synclines underline the
352 basement depressions. The geometry of the folds is tighter in depth and more open in the most recent
353 sedimentary units. Domes and anticlinal ridges are the geomorphological features resulting from this
354 sedimentary folding. The high density of normal faults on the basement ridges produces scarps and terraces
355 on the seafloor. The main faults in the sediment cover are rooted at basement blocks boundaries whose
356 top surface deeps in a seaward direction (Fig. 10D). Sub-vertical attenuated amplitude zones related to fluid
357 migration pathways are observed at the top of the main domes (Fig. 10D).

358

359

360 **5.4. Tectono-volcanic reliefs**

361 5.4.1. Bulges

362 Only one bulge has been observed in the study area (the Garoé Bulge). It is located at 4,952 mwd in the
363 central WCS (Fig. 11C) with a kilometeric-scale. This bulge is 78 m high, has a gentle slope gradient reaching
364 a maximum of 3.5° (Table 3) and has an elliptical shape, being affected by depressions and normal faults at

365 its summit and on its flanks (Fig. 12). The VHR parametric data show an irregular seafloor defined by parallel
 366 and continuous reflections covering a deformed layer (10-12 ms TWT) of transparent acoustic facies. The
 367 MCS profiles show a main NE-SW linear axial depression (1–3.5 km wide and 25 m deep) deep-rooted (1.1
 368 s TWT) along two major faults (Fig. 12).

369

Types	N	D_{min} (mwd)	D_{avg} (mwd)	D_{max} (mwd)	S_{min} (°)	S_{avg} (°)	S_{max} (°)	H_{avg} (m)	Θ (°)	ρ_{min} (dB)	ρ_{avg} (dB)	ρ_{max} (dB)
Bulge	1	4,849	4,895	4,952	0.005	0.7	3.5	78	50	-55	-30	-8
Dome	29	4,905	4,930	4,953	0.1	1.7	4.5	48	75	-38	-26	-17
Irregular domes	34	3,950	4,110	5,050	0.1	1.7	5.3	76	79	-9	-6	-4
Mound	172	4,800	4,889	4,939	0.5	4,6	12.9	139	53	-37	-26	-13
Hill	16	4,316	4,697	4,905	0.5	11,2	33.6	589	74	-49	-24	-3
Seamount	7	1,793	3,213	4,122	0.2	14,8	38.1	2328	120	-37	-14	-0.06

370

371 **Table 3.-** Morphometric parameters of the sub-circular positive reliefs mapped in the study area. N, number of features; D_{min} ,
 372 minimum depth in mwd; D_{avg} , average depth in mwd; D_{max} , maximum depth in mwd; S_{min} , average minimum slope gradient in
 373 degrees; S_{avg} , average slope gradient in degrees; S_{max} , average maximum slope gradient in degrees; Θ , average azimuth in
 374 degrees; H_{avg} , height in metres; ρ_{min} , minimum reflectivity in dB, ρ_{avg} , average reflectivity in dB, ρ_{max} , maximum reflectivity in dB.

375

376 5.4.2. Domes

377 The domes (“d” in Fig. 3) are smooth, positive sub-circular edifices over a deformed antiform substrate.
 378 They are restricted to the central part of the WCS, also known as the Subvent Area (Fig. 11A and 11C). Some
 379 of them are distinctively grouped in a crowded cluster, whereas others are isolated or in pairs. Often, the
 380 merging of various domes generates elongated shapes, predominantly along NE-SW. The domes have mean
 381 heights of 48 m and an average slope gradient of 1.7° (Table 3). The summits are smooth and the flanks are
 382 occasionally irregular with circular slide scars and small slide deposits at their bases. Some structures are

383 controlled by reverse faults (Fig. 13 B and “TC” in Fig. 13C) that are taller and steeper and have higher
384 diameters and irregularity than the ones not controlled by faults (Fig. 13 D and “NTC” in Fig. 13C). Both the
385 fault-controlled and the non-fault-controlled domes have sub-parallel and continuous reflections of high
386 amplitude over lenses of blanking acoustic facies of 20 to 30 ms TWT in thickness (“bf” in Fig. 13B and 13D).
387 In the majority of cases, they show internally vertical columns of chaotic acoustic facies (“cf” in Fig. 13B).
388 Well-layered undulating reflections, locally highly deformed, are observed to surround the domes and are
389 onlapped by parallel and flat reflections from 15 to 30 ms TWT in thickness (Fig. 13B and 13D).

390 5.4.3. Irregular domes

391 More than 30 irregular domes have been recognized (Table 3) mainly at the base of the slope of El
392 Hierro and La Palma islands (“id” in Fig. 3). To the west, they appear more scattered and deeper up to 5,050
393 mwd. At the base of the volcanic islands, they show a chaotic distribution with no clear orientation (“id” in
394 Fig. 3). They show a flattened relief (76 m in mean height and 5 to 10 km in diameter), an irregular lobate
395 perimeter and a very smooth summit (0.1°–1° slope gradient) and gentle flanks (1.5°–5.3°). The VHR
396 parametric profiles show parallel continuous reflections of high amplitude above them. In the MCS profiles
397 passing 1 to 2 km from these structures, the irregular domes appear to be linked to deep-rooted anticlines
398 and sub-vertical faults (Fig. 13A).

399

400

401 5.5. Volcanic edifices

402 5.5.1. Mounds

403 The mounds are volcanic edifices (less than 500 m high) built by extrusion events of hydrothermal or
404 magmatic origin and are widely distributed in most of the eastern Canary Basin geomorphological domains.
405 They are mainly distributed in mound trails in the MDCS and WCS, although isolated edifices are also
406 observed at medium depths in the WCS and surrounding higher edifices in the southern CVP. At least 13

407 mound trails are identified following the WNW-ESE trend, parallel to the direction of the oceanic fracture
408 zones and among the distributary channels of the MDCS (“4” in Fig. 2). On the central and southern WCS,
409 the mounds are clustered (Figs. 9, 11A and 14F) in small chains and in pairs (following the WNW-ESE trend).
410 Some of the mounds display an opposite NNE-SSW predominant orientation in their axis (Fig. 11D). They
411 have a mean height of 139 m, average maximum slopes of 12.9° and extreme maximum values of 39° (Table
412 3). These edifices have variable shapes ranging from sub-circular cones to mostly irregular and elongated
413 ridges. The former have smooth to slightly pointed summits. The elongated ridges display crests and multi-
414 peaked summits (Fig. 11C) and are widely affected by slide scars and gullies.

415 The majority of reported mounds have been classified as volcanic crests. They are far more numerous
416 (165 edifices) than the volcanic cones (only 7 edifices and restricted to the central and southern WCS). In
417 mean values, the volcanic crests are higher, steeper and longer than the volcanic cones, except in the
418 central WCS area, where the volcanic cones are higher and steeper-sloped than the volcanic crests. In the
419 VHR seismic profiles, the volcanic mounds show a bicone structure with chaotic seismic facies with down-
420 bending reflections (inward-dipping) surround them (Fig. 14A)..

421 5.5.2. Hills

422 The hills (Fig. 11) are volcanic edifices (between 500 and 1000 m high) mostly located in the MDCS (“sh”
423 in Fig. 2), the northern WCS (“sh” in Fig. 9) and the southern CIVP (“sh” in Fig. 7). In the MDCS and WCS,
424 they are randomly distributed between the mound trails following a WNW-ESE alignment. The hills have a
425 mean height of 589 m and their flanks have a slope of 27° to 39° (the average maximum slope is 33.6°; Table
426 3). They show mainly irregular shapes with smooth summits. In the WCS, elongated hills are observed in
427 the track of linear ridges showing composited summits. Their flanks have arcuate scars and are crossed by
428 gullies (“as” in Fig. 7B). Locally, seafloor irregularities have been identified at the piedmonts of the hills.

429 In the southern CIVP, Infinito, Pelicar, Malpaso and Tortuga submarine hills (Fig. 7A) are also WNW-ESE
430 aligned, but in this case with the south of The Paps and Ico seamounts. They show an ellipsoidal plan and a
431 smooth relief with rounded summits of 1° to 7° and steep slopes at the base (15°-28°). Malpaso is the

432 biggest (ca. 750 m high with a projected area of ca. 34 km²). Gullies have only been found on Tortuga (Figs.
433 7A and 7B), the steepest-sloped submarine hill. As in the Ico seamount, some arcuate scars and circular
434 cones of high backscatter character have been mapped (Fig. 7A and 7B).

435 5.5.3. Seamounts

436 Seven seamounts (Table 3) (Las Hijas [Fig. 3], Bimbache, Echo, The Paps, Ico, Drago and Tropic [Fig. 7])
437 are observed in the study area, all of them located in the southern CIVP (Fig. 1B). They show a mean height
438 of 2,328 m and an average maximum slope gradient of 38.1° (Table 3). Their shapes tend to range from
439 elongated to complex edifices.

440 Morphological lineaments of seamounts are common in the study area. Las Hijas is a set of three NE-
441 SW aligned seamounts (Fig. 1A, 1B and 3). Bimbache and The Paps are N-S elongated, whereas Echo and
442 Tropic are sub-circular. Drago and Ico are NNW-SSE and NW-SE ellipsoidal volcanic edifices, respectively
443 (Fig. 7A).

444 Several highly reflective cones are observed on the top and flanks of the seamounts (red dots in Fig.
445 7A). These cones, with a high seafloor backscatter strength, have small diameters (from 0.5 to 2 km) and
446 are up to 120 m high (Figs. 7C and 7I).

447 The flanks of the seamounts show eroded slide scars and arcuate escarpments (e.g. Echo and Tropic
448 seamounts) 7 to 9 km long (up to 15 km on the Echo seamount), as well as incised linear gullies (4–15 km
449 long and with a talweg width of 0.5–1.5 km) that continue downslope to the deep basin along submarine
450 channels (Fig. 7A). The flanks of the Tropic seamount are separated by linear ridges 10 to 13 km long and
451 are sourced from composite arcuate headwall escarpments (Fig. 7E).

452 Wedges of MTDs with transparent acoustic facies are observed at the foot of slope of these seamounts
453 (Figs. 7A and 15) coming from their flanks. In the VHR parametric profiles, they occur as buried wedges with
454 regular and homogeneous hyperbolas at depths varying according to their location. They are mainly at 9 to
455 16 ms TWT bsf (e.g. surrounding The Paps seamount; Fig. 15A). Locally, they reach deeper locations, as in

456 the Tropic and Bimbache seamounts, at 40 and 55 ms TWT, respectively (Fig. 15C). On the Echo seamount,
457 two high backscatter lobes of MTDs with a transparent facies are located on the seafloor in the northern
458 and southern parts of the base of slope of the seamount (Fig. 15B).

459 The Echo and Tropic seamounts are flat-topped cone guyots with terraced boundaries (“T” in Figs. 7D
460 and 7E). The number of levels of terraces are different in the west and east sides. On the west side only one
461 or two levels are observed, whilst on the eastern and northeastern sides at least seven levels of terraces
462 are present (from 340 to 480 mwd on the Echo seamount and from 1,005 to 1,835 mwd on the Tropic
463 seamount).

464

465

466 6. DISCUSSION: THE ROLE OF TECTONICS IN SEDIMENT DYNAMICS AND RELIEF BUILDING

467 6.1. Deep-rooted oceanic control of faults, folds and minor volcanic reliefs

468 The eastern Canary Basin shows two clear structural trends (WNW-ESE and NNE-SSW) controlling the
469 majority of geomorphic features from about 4,250 mwd to the abyssal plain. These trends correspond to
470 the morphostructural expression of the oceanic fabric.

471 6.1.1. WNW-ESE and W-E trend

472 The WNW-ESE and W-E trends match the main oceanic fracture zones that segment the basin. In the
473 distal part of the MDCS and WCDFS, the WNW-ESE and W-E trends control the direction of the turbidite
474 channels (Figs. 2 and 4C) and the location and direction of the lobes of the MTDs (Figs. 2 and 3). In particular,
475 the direction of branches II, III and IV changes sharply from NW-SE (in their proximal sectors) to WNW-ESE
476 (for branch II) (Fig. 2) and W-E (for branches III and IV) (see their middle sectors in Fig. 3) at a depth of 4,850,
477 4,450 and 4,250 mwd, respectively, matching the tracks of the oceanic fracture zones.

478 The distal sector of branch II, from about 4,850 mwd, has linear WNW-ESE boundaries along narrow
479 turbidite channels. In the middle sectors of branches III and IV, from about 4,450 and 4,250 mwd
480 respectively, turbidite channels also follow linear (in this case W-E) tracks but draw a wider channel with an
481 anastomosed and braided second network of smaller superimposed channels (“ch” in Fig. 6) with middle to
482 low backscatter strength (Fig. 6A).

483 The VHR seismic profiles revealed that the MTDs of the WCDFS (mainly along the WNW-ESE and W-E
484 sectors) fill smooth valleys generated by tectonic depressions controlled by mainly monocline folds) and
485 sub-vertical faults (Figs. 5, 6 and 8) deep-rooted in the oceanic basement (Fig. 5C).

486 We infer that the WNW-ESE and W-E trends reflects the fabric of the oceanic fracture zones and
487 controls the location of the MTDs. MCS and the alignment of the volcanic and tectono-volcanic reliefs to
488 this trend (Figs. 1, 9-11) confirms that the fault system is deep-rooted.

489 6.1.2. NNE-SSW trend

490 From north to south, a NNE-SSW trending geomorphic fabric is present in the west portion of the study
491 area, constituted by multiple minor-scale lineaments. This fabric is underlined by the presence of areas of
492 parallel cluster of structural reliefs (fault scarps and anticlines) and mounds (mainly volcanic crests)
493 separated by perpendicular stripes that break their lateral continuity. Although the NNE-SSW trend is
494 clearly evident in the volcanic crest of the MDCS and WCS, the structural reliefs seem to be blurry (Fig. 9).
495 In the distal sector of the MDCS, some NNE-SSW trends are only inferred by geomorphology. The location
496 of some FSLs of MTDs at the end of the turbidite channels matches an increase in the slope gradient (Fig.
497 2C). These knickpoints seem to follow the NNE-SSW trend and are controlled by smooth folds and sub-
498 vertical faults in the VHR parametric profiles.

499 In the WCS, the NNE-SSW oceanic fabric matches linear scarps, ridges and bulges, terraces and
500 submarine hills. These morphological features are controlled by normal faults, monoclines and anticlines
501 that usually show a zone of intense sub-vertical faulting of their hinges (Fig 10). This tectonic fabric also
502 controls the bulges, domes and volcanic reliefs (Figs. 12, 13 and 14). In MCS profiles, the NNE-SSW structures

503 controlling the structural reliefs are deep-rooted in the oceanic basement (Fig. 10D) with the downthrown
504 block seaward, as evidenced by Medialdea et al. (2017) and Reston et al. (2004). We infer that the NNE-
505 SSW trend reveals the oceanic fabric related to the ridge axis fabric (the abyssal hill fabric), which reflects
506 the oceanic basement blocks controlled by normal faults perpendicular to the oceanic fracture zone.

507 Finally, although the irregular domes do not show a clear seafloor trend (e.g. WNW-ESE or NNE-SSE),
508 they show a deep-rooted tectonic control along faults and folds that point to a tectonic or sub-volcanic
509 origin (Fig. 13A).

510

511 6.1.3. Significance of blanking acoustic facies and stripes of low backscatter

512 In the WCS, the reflectivity response observed on the backscatter mosaic is characterized by continuous
513 NNE-SSW stripes of low backscattering strength ("bf" in Fig. 9A). These stripes are located only on the crests
514 of anticlines, reflecting trapped fluids rather than changes in lithology, slope gradient or sedimentary
515 environments that could lead to abrupt textural changes on the seafloor.

516 The multibeam system penetrates the sediment column, and each backscatter mosaic pixel shows the
517 reflectivity of a variable volume of the seafloor depending on the depth. In the Baltic Sea (Bornholm Basin)
518 at 80 m water depth, the multibeam system (Kongsberg EM120 - 12 kHz, hull-mounted) can penetrate more
519 than 12 m (von Deimling et al., 2013). In the study area, TOPAS seismic profiles have revealed that the
520 penetration of the EM122 (12kHz) reaches 40 to 50 ms TWT (ca. 30-35m) at about 3500 to 4000 m water
521 depth. Here, the continuous NNE-SSW stripes of low backscattering strength systematically match the
522 acoustic blanking facies (at 40-50 ms TWT) located in the axial part of smooth anticlines ("bf" in Fig. 10). In
523 addition, these acoustic blanking facies are also observed at the top and on the surrounding domes and
524 bulge structures ("bf" in Figs. 12A, 13B and 13D). We therefore correlate these two acoustic responses with
525 the same phenomena, and subsequently with the presence of fluids inside the sediment. Three possible
526 sources were considered for these fluids: dewatering fluids of buried MTDs, hydrothermal fluids and

527 abiogenic volatiles. (i) The dewatering fluids would be related to buried and compacted MTDs. Some fluid
528 escape structures have been observed in the MTDs coming from the CIVP (Figs. 4C and 8A). Although no
529 MTDs were observed below the stripes of low backscattering strength in the VHR parametric profiles,
530 deeper MTDs have been observed in multichannel seismic profiles related to the WCDFS (León et al., 2019).
531 The blanking acoustic facies could therefore be related to lateral-vertical fluid migration from these deeper
532 MTDs. (ii) The hydrothermal fluids would originate from hydrothermal domes and scattered volcanoes
533 related to a huge, intrusive Quaternary magmatic sill complex together with volcanic activity in this sector
534 of the Canary Basin (Medialdea et al., 2017; Sánchez-Guillamón et al., 2018a, 2018b). Several acoustic
535 blanking facies are observed on the MCS profiles, deep-rooted in the oceanic basement and bright spot
536 anomalies (possibly sills) and migrating along normal faults (Figs. 5C, 10D, 13A and 13C). In the case of the
537 volcanic mounds, the seismic chimneys show chaotic seismic facies. This magmatic activity, related to a
538 mantle plume (hotspot) upwelling off the NW African lithosphere, generated recurrent melting anomalies
539 over time, giving rise to the formation of seamounts from Late Jurassic to Recent times (Geldmacher et al.,
540 2005; van den Bogaard, 2013). Finally, (iii) the abiotic volatiles must be related to serpentinization processes
541 caused by seawater percolation along oceanic fracture zones, where they reach ~11 to 13 km depth. The
542 evolution of a fault zone structure induced by deep fluid-rock interaction on the oceanic fracture zones
543 results in weakening and strain localization within the oceanic lithosphere, providing a large reservoir of
544 volatiles (Prigent et al., 2020).

545 Based on this seismic evidence, we argue that the source of fluids is related to hydrothermal or
546 magmatic processes. The MTDs could work as secondary reservoirs for these fluids. Abiotic volatiles, related
547 to serpentinization processes, are considered as another source, although less likely and restricted to areas
548 where no hydrothermal or magmatic processes have been detected.

549

550

551 **6.2. Geomorphological insights into tectonic activity and volcanic reactivation**

552 6.2.1. Geomorphological insights into seamounts and guyots

553 The flat summits of the studied guyots (the Tropic and Echo seamounts) show a mounded relief in the
554 central part with conical edifices (Fig. 7I). Samples recovered in these cones show benthic communities
555 (Palomino et al., 2016). These cones could reveal a volcanic reactivation after the sinking of the seamount
556 below sea-level. After this reactivation and in an inactive period, we argue that these cones were colonized
557 by benthic communities and further modified by oceanic bottom current (Palomino et al., 2016). Tectonic
558 movements could be inferred in these guyots during the thermal subsidence. The flat summits of the guyots
559 shows a tilting: to the W in the Echo seamount and to the SW in the Tropic seamount. Moreover, the
560 different number of terrace levels between the W and E sides surrounding these flat summits (“T” in Figs.
561 7D-7G) reflects a rotation and tilting of the volcanic edifice during the sinking (thermal subsidence). Signs
562 of this tectonic activity in the Tropic seamount could be the NE-SW and NW-SE striking lineaments located
563 in the seamount settlement.

564 Patches of high seafloor backscattering strength are common in the Drago, The Paps, Echo and Ico
565 seamounts and match small conical reliefs of ca. 1 km in diameter. The presence of these numerous cones
566 could be explained as a non-channelized volcanic reactivation. Thus, multiple small volcanic cones can result
567 from a network of magmatic pathways instead of a single, larger magmatic chamber. This volcanic typology
568 of magma extrusion has often been observed in large volcanic edifices, which are built over long-lived
569 periods along several volcanic foci instead of during short-lived volcanic phases such as those detected in
570 small volcanic edifices (Batiza and Vanko, 1983).

571

572 6.2.2. Ages of reactivation and latent periods

573 Volcanic activity and flank collapses in the volcanic edifices are closely related (Hunt and Jarvis, 2017;
574 León et al., 2019). Seafloor arcuate structures on the seamount flanks above the MTDs point to scar failures
575 (Fig. 7D and 7E). The star-shaped morphology on the summits of the guyots seems to be produced by the

576 slope failures along debris avalanches (Mitchell, 2001; Vogt and Smoot, 1984). In addition, several MTD
577 levels are detected downslope from these headwall scars. The VHR parametric profiles show that they are
578 mostly buried below a variable thickness of alternating high-amplitude continuous reflections (Fig. 15A).

579 We correlate the MTDs at the foot of slope of the seamounts and the headwall scars at their summit as
580 belonging to the same instability processes. They are also genetically associated, in part, with the other
581 MTDs of the southern system of the WCDFS. In the Canary Islands and Great Meteor seamounts, periods
582 of intensive volcanism are related to periods of flank collapses and generation of turbidite layers on the
583 Madeira Abyssal Plain (Hunt and Jarvis, 2017). In particular, to the west of La Palma and El Hierro islands,
584 the massive gravitational instabilities belonging to the WCDFS are related to the critical volcanic period of
585 the Canary Island in the middle to upper Miocene ($\sim 13.5 \pm 1.2$ Ma) (León et al., 2019). Based on the
586 geomorphological insights described above, such as volcanic cones on the guyot surfaces, patches of high
587 seafloor backscattering on the seamounts and landslide processes (possibly debris avalanches) on their
588 flanks, the southern CIVP does not seem to have been inactive since the Cretaceous, as postulated by van
589 den Boogard (2013). We argue that this volcanic-tectonic reactivation could be related to that observed in
590 the Canary archipelago, which generated the onset of the WCDFS ~ 13.5 Ma ago.

591 The volcanic processes in the seamounts of the CIVP seem to be inactive at present. The volcanic cones
592 on the guyot surfaces are colonized by bioconstruction (Palomino et al., 2016), and the MTDs of the
593 southern system of the WCDFS are majority buried. Only one MTD has been detected over seafloor in the
594 northern flank of Echo seamount (Fig. 7D). In the southern system of the WCDFS, the MTDs are buried at a
595 variable thickness of sediments from ~ 10 to 25 ms TWT (Figs. 8 and 15A), except at the foot of the slope of
596 the Tropic seamount, where the MTDs are ~ 40 ms TWT deep (Fig. 15C). Taking into account an average
597 seismic velocity of 1550 to 1600 ms^{-1} and a sedimentation rate of ~ 2.3 cm/ky (Firth et al., 1996), we
598 established at 339 to 869 kyr (–Lower-Middle Pleistocene) the onset of a latent period of gravitational
599 instabilities without MTDs in the sediment column. This onset is older on the Tropic seamount (~ 1.35 Ma;
600 Lower Pleistocene).

601 We therefore suggest a period of volcano-tectonic reactivation from the middle–upper Miocene to the
602 Lower–Middle Pleistocene on the southern CIVP in the eastern Canary Basin. This period matches with the
603 main period of volcanic building in Canary Islands ([Ancochea et al., 2004](#)) and sill intrusions in Cabo Verde
604 archipelago ([Duncan and Jackson, 1978](#)). In this period, several volcano-tectonic processes took place that
605 changed the seafloor relief, including the generation of (i) volcanic eruptions on the WCS and MDCS
606 (mounds and hills) and on the southern CIVP, such as the volcanic cones on top of guyot surfaces and the
607 patches of high seafloor backscattering strength on the seamounts (e.g. The Paps or Drago); (ii) tectono-
608 volcanic reliefs (bulges, domes and irregular domes); (iii) structural lineaments (linear ridges and
609 escarpments); and (iv) large flank collapses in volcanic islands (La Palma and El Hierro) and seamounts (e.g.
610 The Paps, Echo and Tropic) and the subsequent extensive incision of the flanks by gullies and MTDs at the
611 foot of slopes of the Drago, The Paps, Echo, Ico and Tropic seamounts.

612 In the Lower Pleistocene, this volcano-tectonic activity decreased to practical inactivity in the southern
613 CIVP. The large MTDs in branches V and VI ceased and the tectonic and volcano-tectonic activity receded
614 to a local and latent activity appearing only as local hydrothermal sites (Subvent Area; [Medialdea et al.,
615 2017](#)), structural reliefs, local seafloor instabilities (e.g. the San Borondón crest; [Fig. 7A](#)) or small flank
616 collapses (e.g. the MTDs to the north of the Echo seamount; [Fig. 7D](#)). Based on only geomorphological
617 indicators, the latent volcano-tectonic activity could be possible extended to the Holocene. These indicators
618 will be: the presence of MTDs without sedimentary seismic reflections above them in the WCDFS and CIVP,
619 Seafloor sediments affected by faults in the WCS (e.g. in the structural reliefs), active incised turbidite
620 channels following the WNW-ESE and W-E trend in MDCS and WCDFS and the presence of Hydrothermal
621 activity in the WCS with an estimated age up to ca. 25Ka ([Medialdea et al., 2017](#)).

622

623 6.2.3. Comparison with similar intraplate domains

624 Other intraplate domains in the world, the control of the oceanic fractures zones in the spatial
625 distribution of volcanic edifices, tectonic reliefs and MTDs has been also observed. In the Tasmantid

626 Seamount Chain (east Australian margin), the morphology of the volcanic edifices is significant controlled
627 by the structural inheritance of the oceanic lithosphere. Elongate seamounts predominantly occur on
628 fracture zones or inside their corners. In addition, the orientation of their feeder magmatic system are
629 controlled by the structure of extinct ridges more than 20 Ma after spreading ceased (Richards et al., 2018).

630 In the Indian Ocean (Wharton Basin), linear ridges and depressions (pull-apart) are generated by the
631 deformation of the sediment column by vertical strike-slip deep-rooted in the oceanic basement and
632 reactivated by existing oceanic fracture zones (Singh et al., 2017b). In the Central Indian Basin, , areas of
633 chaotic seismic facies correlated with MTDs appear confined to oceanic fracture zones or closures of
634 anticline folds (Levchenko and Verzhbitskii, 2005). These oceanic fracture zones also control the location of
635 seamounts (Sborshchikov et al., 1995). Finally, In the Pacific Ocean, sediment column extensionally
636 deformed with associated hydrothermal systems has been reported in the Clarion – Cliperton oceanic
637 fractures zone (Yubko and Lygina, 2015).

638

639 **6.3. Proposed tectono-stratigraphic model for the Eastern Canary Basin since middle-upper** 640 **Miocene to Lower-Middle Pleistocene**

641 Based on the geomorphological evidence, a model is presented in order to explain their origin and
642 distribution of different geomorphological features observed. From the middle–upper Miocene to at least
643 the Lower–Middle Pleistocene, an uplift and volcano-tectonic reactivation is proposed for the southern
644 CIVP (Fig. 16). Locally, this reactivation could reach a younger age (perhaps Holocene) in reference to the
645 seafloor fractures and deformations observed in the Garoé Bulge, the incision of turbidite channels following
646 seafloor fractures, the Quaternary magmatic and hydrothermal activity reported in several submarine hills
647 of the WCS (e.g. the Subvent Area; Medialdea et al., 2017; Sánchez-Guillamón et al., 2018b) and the seafloor
648 instabilities observed on the San Borondón crest or to the north of the Echo seamount.

649 This volcano-tectonic reactivation affects the deep-rooted NNE-SSW and WNW-ESE/W-E fractures. The
650 vertical motion observed in the WNW-ESE and W-E oceanic fracture zone fabric controls: (i) the
651 emplacement of the MTDs in the tectonic depressions (fault-controlled synclinal structures) that have been
652 generated on the flanks of the volcanic edifices, and (ii) the location of focused and minor volcanic centres
653 such as mounds and hills.

654 The seafloor expression of the deep-rooted NNE-SSW fractures is inconsistent with a classic thermal
655 subsidence model as should happen in this area, given the Mesozoic age of the oceanic lithosphere (Ranero
656 et al., 1997). Geomorphological evidence suggests that a regional uplift in the eastern Canary Basin is
657 responsible for the normal reactivation of the basement fractures with an induced rotation (Fig. 16B) and
658 the subsequent formation of the seafloor morphostructural NNE-SSW fabric. This uplift could originate
659 through thermal expansion by reheating of the lithosphere in this sector of the Canary Basin, which is
660 supported by the decreasing thickness of the lithosphere described by Ranero et al. (1995) and the
661 development of a Quaternary magmatic and hydrothermal system in this area (Medialdea et al., 2017).

662 Causes for this reactivation are related to the long-lived thermal anomaly in the CIVP (Geldmacher et
663 al., 2005; van den Bogaard, 2013). In the WCS, this anomaly could be influenced by the oceanic fracture
664 zones. Geoid anomalies in oceanic fracture zones indicate the occurrence of small-scale convective
665 instabilities (Cadio and Korenaga, 2014) that may be related to the activation energy associated with small-
666 scale convection (Cadio and Korenaga, 2016). Furthermore, in oceanic fracture zones, the lithosphere flexes
667 in response to stresses from the differential subsidence across the fracture (Bonatti, 1978; Johnston et al.,
668 2011) and control of later volcanism (Epp, 1984). Many oceanic fracture zones are characterized by the
669 presence of numerous volcanoes, which indicate weakness and exhibit “flexure” profiles versus “slipped”
670 or volcanic constructional profiles (Lowrie et al., 1986).

671 In areas between ocean fracture zones, lithospheric stresses are induced by mantle flow and tractions,
672 crustal heterogeneity and topography (Lithgow-Bertelloni and Guynn, 2004), as well as changes in the
673 direction of spreading with regard to the direction (or curvature) of the fracture zone (Bonatti, 1978). The

674 occurrence of marked reliefs in the bathymetry associated with oceanic fracture zones, in segments of the
675 oceanic lithosphere where their influence should not be so marked, has been explained by the development
676 of intense vertical tectonics affecting upper mantle and crustal blocks along these zones of oceanic
677 weakness (Bonatti, 1978). Vertical motion associated with oceanic fracture zones has been also explained
678 by different subsidence rates of crust of an offset age (and therefore density) (De Long et al., 1977). Several
679 factors could be associated with the vertical motions along the oceanic fracture zones, such as horizontal
680 heat conduction across a fracture zone, visco-dynamic forces, serpentinite diapirism and compressional and
681 tensional horizontal stresses (Bonatti, 1978).

682 After the Lower–Middle Pleistocene, an inactive (locally latent) volcanic period began in the eastern
683 Canary Basin. Volcanic activity ceased, as did the emplacement of massive MTDs coming from the flanks of
684 volcanic islands and seamounts. Based on: (i) geomorphological indicators (incision of WNW turbidite
685 channels or the lobes of the presence of MTDs over seafloor without reflection over them) and (ii) local
686 hydrothermal activity in the Subvent Area (Medialdea et al., 2017) and the foot of slope of El Hierro Island
687 (Urgeles et al., 1997); we suggest that this volcano-tectonic activity has remained latent, possibly up to
688 Holocene.

689

690 7. CONCLUSIONS

- 691 • Four main geomorphological domains have been defined in the eastern Canary Basin characterized
692 by different geomorphological features and processes: the MDCS, the WCS, the southern CIVP and
693 the WCDFS.

694 The MDCS is characterized by the presence of a complex linear turbidite channel system; the WCS
695 by a very smooth general slope gradient of 0.04° to 0.15° broken locally by structural and minor
696 volcanic reliefs; the southern CIVP by the presence of seamounts, guyots and submarine hills; and

697 the WCDFS by six connected branches of MTDs that extend more than 200,000 km² from the base
698 of the western flanks of the western Canary Islands and seamounts to the Madeira Abyssal Plain.

699 • The geomorphological features in the above domains show evidence of a volcanic and tectonic
700 reactivation from the middle–upper Miocene to the Lower–Middle Pleistocene (possible Holocene)
701 spread over the whole of the eastern Canary Basin that reached the western Canary Islands (La
702 Palma and El Hierro Islands). This reactivation is especially important in the seamount province of
703 CIVP reported inactive since Cretaceous.

704 • The location and morphology of these geomorphological features are controlled by two tectonic
705 lineaments trending WNW-ESE and NNE-SSW:

706 ○ The WNW-ESE trend matches the track of the oceanic fracture zones mapped in the study
707 area and controls: (i) the location and direction of the linear turbidite channels in the MDCS
708 and the distal part of the WCDFS; (ii) the lateral continuity of structural reliefs (cutting
709 them) in the WCS; (iii) the direction of aligned submarine hills and seamounts in the WCS
710 and the southern CIVP; and (iv) the direction of the lobes of the MTDs in the WCDFS.

711 ○ The NNE-SSW trend matches normal fractures delimiting blocks of oceanic crust between
712 the oceanic fracture zones. This trend controls the direction of the main structural reliefs
713 in the eastern Canary Basin, such as terraced escarpments, linear ridges of monoclines and
714 anticlines, linear normal-faulted escarps and volcanic ridges.

715 • A tecto-sedimentary model of volcano-tectonic reactivation in oceanic intraplate domains is
716 proposed (for the above mentioned period) in which sedimentary, tectonic and volcanic geological
717 processes are interconnected. A tectonic uplift in the eastern Canary Basin and western Canary
718 Islands (La Palma and El Hierro), and the associated thermal anomaly, triggered volcanic and
719 hydrothermal activity and subsequent flank collapse processes, and the emplacement of MTDs on
720 the WCDFS. The uplift reworked normal basement structures (as well as oceanic fracture zones) on

721 the WCS, generating seafloor deformations (folds and faults) that control the location of the MTDs
722 and the volcanic/hydrothermal activity in the eastern Canary Basin.

723 • This tecto-sedimentary model can be applied in other oceanic intraplate domains of the world, where
724 tectonic uplift, volcanic/hydrothermal activity and the subsequent flank collapse and emplacement of
725 mass transport deposits could take place.

726

727 **8. DATA AVAILABILITY**

728 As mentioned in Data and Methodology section, all datasets except the Leg SUBVENT1 of the
729 SUBVENT1-MAEC cruise are classified as “restricted” by the Spanish Foreign Ministry. The SUBVENT1-MAEC
730 cruise was composed of two Legs: SUBVENT1 and MAEC. The aim of SUBVENT1, funded by the Spanish
731 scientific project SUBVENT (CGL2012-39524-C02), was to study the submarine fluid emission systems in the
732 Canary Basin; and the aim of MAEC, funded by the Spanish Special Action (CTM2010-09496-E), was to
733 recover data to the west of the CIVP as a basis for the proposal submitted by Spain to the Commission on
734 the Limits of the Continental Shelf (United Nations) named “Partial Submission of Data and Information on
735 the Limits of the Continental Shelf of Spain to the West of the Canary Islands, pursuant to Part VI and Annex
736 II of United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea”.

737 The data used in this paper belonging to SUBVENT1-MAEC_2013 are located in the data repository at
738 <http://www.repositorio.ieo.es/e-ieo/handle/10508/11548>. The owner of these data is the Instituto Español
739 de Oceanografía (IEO). The current situation of these data with regard to the SUBVENT1 leg in the repository
740 is that they are available on request.

741

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759

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974 **Figure Captions**

975 **Fig 1.-** Regional overview of the study area. A) Location and geological map of the study area. B)
976 Geomorphological domains: I to V (in red), branches of the Western Canary Debris Flow System; red dotted
977 line, study area. C) Data used in the work: black lines, topographic parametric sonar (TOPAS); red lines,
978 multichannel seismic; coloured surface, multibeam data (bathymetry and backscatter); white dotted line,
979 non-restricted data belonging to the SUBVENT1 leg of the SUBVENT1-MAEC cruise; WCS, Western Canary
980 Slope; CIVP, Canary Islands Volcanic Province; WCDFS, Western Canary Debris Flow System; MDCS, Madeira
981 Distributary Channel System.

982 **Fig 2.-** Distal parts of the MDCS and the WCDFS. A) Backscatter mosaic and geological mapping overlapped:
983 white lines, turbidite channels; white arrows, flow direction; yellow lines, lobes of MTDs. B)
984 Geomorphological studied features of the distal parts of the MDCS and the WCDFS: purple line, bathymetric
985 vs slope gradient profiles in **Figure 2C**; box in black dotted line, backscatter detail box; red lines, location of
986 **Figures 4C, 5B and 14B**; black arrows, turbidite channel NW-SE trend; grey arrows, turbidite channel WSW-
987 ENE trend; red roman numbers, branches I and II of the WCDFS. Legend: 1, thin fan-shaped lobes of MTDs;
988 2, recent MTDs (on the seafloor); 3, buried MTDs; 4, volcanic edifice: mound and submarine hill (sh); 5,
989 piedmont; 6, contact; 7, inferred contact; 8, turbidite channels; 9, geomorphological inferred trend
990 (knickpoints); 10, oceanic fracture zone; 11, 12 and 13, structural lineaments (11 and 12, escarpments; 11
991 structural escarpment generated by fault [fault with morphological expression]; 12, generic structural
992 escarpment; 13, linear ridge [anticline]); 14, sedimentary paths. C) Bathymetric (purple) vs slope gradient
993 (blue) profiles. kp, knickpoints.

994 **Fig 3.-** Geomorphological studied features of the northern system of the WCDFS: proximal part of branches
995 I, II, III and IV (in red roman numbers). Location of **Figures 4D, 5D and 6A**. Legend: 1, thin fan-shaped lobes
996 of MTDs; 2, recent MTDs (on the seafloor); 3, buried MTDs; 4, volcanic edifices and tectono-volcanic reliefs
997 (mound, seamount [sm], submarine hill [sh], bulge [bg], dome [d] and irregular dome [id]); 5, contact; 6,

998 erosional scarp; 7, turbidite channels; 8, 9 and 10, structural lineaments (8 and 9, escarpments; 8 structural
999 escarpment generated by fault [fault with morphological expression]; 9, generic structural escarpment; 10,
1000 linear ridge [anticline]); 11, oceanic fracture zone; 12, headwall escarpment (landslide); 13, submarine
1001 landslide; 14, sedimentary paths. DA: Debris Avanche.

1002 **Fig 4.-** Turbidite channels. Backscatter mosaics (dark, high values) with geomorphological interpretation
1003 overlapped and VHR parametric profiles in the MDCS (A), (B) and (C) and the WCDFS (D) and (E). White
1004 lines, turbidite channels; white arrows, flow direction; yellow lines, lobes of MTDs. (A), (B) and (C),
1005 geomorphological interpretation overlapped on backscatter mosaic (A) and VHR parametric profile (B) and
1006 (C) of the distal facies of the MDCS. (B) Zoom detailed of (C). MTDs, mass-transport deposits; fsl, fan-shaped
1007 lobes of debrites; hb1 and hb2, high backscatter lobes of MTDs belonging to the distal facies of branch II;
1008 ch1, turbidite channel; esc, escarpment; disc, unconformity; OFZ, approximate location of the oceanic
1009 fracture zone mapped from gravity and magnetic anomalies (red dot line in backscatter mosaics). (D) and
1010 (E), geomorphological interpretation overlapped on the backscatter mosaic (D) and the VHR parametric
1011 profile (E) of the proximal sector of the vertical staked lobes of MTDs and turbidite channels belonging to
1012 branches I and II. I, branch I; II, branch II; ch1 and ch2, wide turbidite channels; I, narrow turbidite channels;
1013 hb, high-reflective lobes of MTDs; mlb, middle-lower reflective lobes of MTDs. Location of seismic profiles
1014 **4C** and **4E** on **Figures 2** and **3**, respectively.

1015 **Fig 5.-** Lobes of MTDs belonging to branches II and III. A) geomorphological interpretation overlapped on
1016 the backscatter mosaic of the distal parts of branch II (WCDFS). B) VHR parametric profiles showing the
1017 tectonic control (folds and faults) in the morphology of the profile and the distribution and location of
1018 MTDs. MTD, mass-transport deposits; hb1 and hb2, high backscatter lobes of MTDs; mb1 and mb2,
1019 moderate backscatter lobes of MTDs; bd, buried lobes of MTDs; ch, channel. C) MCS profile cutting branch
1020 III of the WCDFS. Normal faults affecting the sediment column deep-rooted in the acoustic (oceanic)
1021 basement. fl, fluid flow pathways. D) geomorphological interpretation overlapped on the backscatter
1022 mosaic of branch III (WCDFS). E) lobes and fan-shaped lobes of the MTDs of branch III. ch, turbidite channel;

1023 hb, high backscatter lobes of MTDs; fsl, fan-shaped lobes of MTDs; bd, buried lobes of MTDs; OFZ,
1024 approximate location of the oceanic fracture zone mapped from gravity and magnetic anomalies. In
1025 backscatter mosaics: dark, high values; light grey and white, low values; white lines, turbidite channels;
1026 white arrows, flow direction; yellow lines, lobes of MTDs. Location of seismic profile 5B on Figure 2 and
1027 seismic profiles 5C and 5D on Figure 3.

1028 **Fig 6.-** Branch IV (WCDFS). A) backscatter mosaic (dark, high values) and geological map overlapped. Yellow
1029 lines, contact between major MTD events on the seafloor; yellow dotted lines, boundaries of single events
1030 with high backscatter contrast; pink dotted lines, buried MTD events; red lines, location of VHR parametric
1031 profiles. In backscatter mosaic and VHR parametric profiles: fsl, fan-shaped lobes of MTDs; hb, high-
1032 reflective lobe of MTDs; bd, buried MTDs; ch, channels; disc, discontinuity. B) VHR parametric profile in the
1033 distal sector showing buried MTD events and fan-shaped lobes of MTDs filling tectonic depressions: as,
1034 arcuate scar. C) VHR parametric profile in the middle sector showing positive relief on high-reflective events
1035 of thick stacked MTDs incised by turbidite channels. D) VHR parametric profile in the proximal sector
1036 showing high-reflective stacked and imbricated MTD events filling a smooth negative relief related to a
1037 tectonic depression and incised by several turbidite channels. Location on Figure 3.

1038 **Fig 7.-** Southern system of the WCDFS and the southern CIVP. A) geomorphological studied features.
1039 Legend: 1, thin fan-shaped lobes of MTDs; 2, recent MTDs (on the seafloor); 3, buried MTDs; 4, volcanic
1040 edifices (mound, seamount [sm] and submarine hill [sh]); 5, piedmont; 6, contact; 7, erosional scarp; 8,
1041 turbidite channel; 9, seamount ridges; 10, 11 and 12, structural lineaments (10 and 11, escarpments; 10
1042 structural escarpment generated by fault [fault with morphological expression], 11, generic structural
1043 escarpment; 12, linear ridge [anticlinal]); 13, oceanic fracture zone, 14, seamount terrace; 15, headwall
1044 escarpment; 16, submarine landslide; 17, sedimentary paths; 18, high-reflective cone. Red roman numbers,
1045 number of branches of the WCDFS. (B) 3D view of the submarine hills (Malpaso, Pelicar and Tortuga) and
1046 the Ico seamount. (C), backscatter mosaic and bathymetric details of The Paps seamount; i, incision by
1047 gullies; hr, high-reflective cones. (G) and (F) bathymetric details of Echo and Tropic seamounts, respectively.

1048 (D) and (E) details of the geomorphological map of the Echo and Topic seamounts, respectively. (H)
1049 bathymetric profile on the summit of Echo seamount showing the terraced profile in the boundary of the
1050 summit; Location on (D) and (I). (I) 3D view of the summit of Echo seamount. "T", escarp of terraces.

1051 **Fig 8.-** VHR parametric profiles crossing the southern system of the WCDFS. (A) and (B) toe of branches VI
1052 and V, respectively. Erosional unconformities (disc) at the base of the blanking acoustic seismic facies
1053 belonging to the MTDs. In A, fluid migration seismic structures at the top of the MTDs. C) profile over a
1054 deep-rooted oceanic fracture zone; stacked lobes of MTDs of branch VI filling tectonic depressions over a
1055 terraced profile generated by a folded and vertically faulted substrate. Location on [Figure 7](#).

1056 **Fig 9.-** Structural lineament mapping in the WCS. A) backscatter mosaic (dark, high values) and
1057 geomorphological interpretation overlapped. Yellow lines, volcanic edifices: mounds and submarine hills
1058 (sh); bf, stripes of blanking acoustic facies; v, short valleys perpendicular to the main direction of the slope;
1059 1, structural escarpment generated by fault (fault with morphological expression); 2, generic structural
1060 escarpments; 3, linear ridge (anticline); dotted blue line, boundary of MTDs (branch III). B) seafloor shade
1061 relief model and structural lineaments over-posted (black dotted lines) with the downthrown block
1062 direction (black arrow); white dashed lines, oceanic fracture zone. In A and B: red lines, location of seismic
1063 profiles of [Figure 10](#).

1064 **Fig 10.-** A, B, C and D) VHR parametric profiles of the WCS. Crests and terraced profile controlled by faults
1065 and anticlines. E) MCS profile (GAI-24) showing deep-rooted domes (white dm) and vertical fractures (black
1066 arrows) controlling the structural reliefs of the WCS. fl and white arrows, fluid migration; gr, minor graben
1067 structures; sf, synthetic faults; bf, blanking acoustic facies; sa, secondary minor anticlines; la, large
1068 anticlines.

1069 **Fig 11.-** Structural reliefs and minor volcanic edifices. A) geographical distribution of the structural reliefs
1070 and minor volcanic edifices in the eastern Canary Basin: i, stripes of structural reliefs separated by oceanic
1071 fracture zones; red lines, location of [Figures 12, 13 and 14](#); red dotted lines, location of parts (B) and (C). B)
1072 3D view of CIVP: in the foreground, blocks at the foot of slope of El Hierro Island; in the background, The

1073 Paps and Bimbache seamounts; red dotted line, location of [Figure 13A](#). C). 3D view and morphological
1074 aspects of the Garoé Bulge, domes and mounds of the Western Canary Slope. Red dotted lines, location of
1075 [Figures 12 and 14C](#). D) Rose diagrams showing the main directions of the structural reliefs and minor
1076 volcanic edifices in the study area.

1077 **Fig 12.-** Tectono-volcanic reliefs: bulge (Garoé). A) VHR parametric profile of bulge: bf, blanking acoustic
1078 facies; td, tectonic depression. B) MCS profile and interpretation: af, antithetic fault; uM-Q, upper Miocene–
1079 Quaternary unit; mM, middle Miocene unit; uE-IC, Upper Eocene–Late Cretaceous unit (Campanian); uC,
1080 Upper Cretaceous (Late Albian–Early Turonian). Location in [Figure 11C](#).

1081 **Fig 13.-** Tectono-volcanic reliefs: domes. A) MCS profile and separate geological interpretation of the
1082 irregular domes at the base of El Hierro Island: id1 and id2, irregular domes; location in [Figure 11B](#). B) VHR
1083 parametric profile of tectonic-controlled domes; location in [Figure 14G](#). C) MCS profile and separate
1084 geological interpretation of non–tectonic-controlled (NTC) and tectonic-controlled (TC) domes; location in
1085 [Figure 14G](#). D) VHR parametric profile of non–tectonic-controlled domes; location in [Figure 11A](#). bf,
1086 blanking acoustic facies; uM-Q, Upper Miocene–Quaternary unit; mM, Middle Miocene unit; uE-IC, Upper
1087 Eocene–Late Cretaceous unit (Campanian); uC, Upper Cretaceous (Late Albian–Early Turonian).

1088 **Fig 14.-** Volcanic reliefs: mounds. A) VHR parametric profile across volcanic mound M01 in the Tres Tenores
1089 area showing extruded deposits in the surroundings, chaotic seismic facies in the chimney and down-
1090 bending reflections. B) VHR parametric profile across volcanic mounds M165 and M187 showing up-
1091 bending reflections in the contact with the sediment column. C) MCS profile and separate geological
1092 interpretation across volcanic mound M02 and M03 in the Tres Tenores area. D) MCS profile and separate
1093 geological interpretation across a volcanic hydrothermal mound. E) 3D view of the Tres Tenores area;
1094 location of (A) and (C). F) Location of (B). G) 3D view of the Subvent Area; location of (D) and [Figures 13B](#)
1095 and [13C](#). cf, chaotic facies; s, sill; vb, volcanic bicone; pf, polygonal faults; db, down-bending reflection; ub,
1096 up-bending reflection; ul, uplift; cf, chaotic facies; uM-Q, Upper Miocene–Quaternary unit; mM, Middle

1097 Miocene unit; uE-IC, Upper Eocene–Late Cretaceous unit (Campanian); uC, Upper Cretaceous (Late Albian–
1098 Early Turonian).

1099 **Fig 15.-** VHR parametric profiles crossing MTDs at the foot of slope of seamount edifices of the CIVP.
1100 Location on **Figure 7**. A) stacked buried lobes of MTDs on the north flank of The Paps seamount. B) high-
1101 reflective transparent lens of MTDs to the north of the Echo seamount. C) transparent acoustic facies on
1102 MTDs over an erosional surface and buried by an alternation of continuous reflections of high amplitude.

1103 **Fig. 16.-** Proposed tecto-sedimentary model from the Middle–Upper Miocene to the Lower–Middle
1104 Pleistocene in the eastern Canary Basin. A). Geological non-scaled scheme showing the structural control
1105 of the ocean fracture zones on the location of both structural reliefs on the Western Canary Slope and mass-
1106 transport deposits sourced from the Canary Islands. B). Geological model showing the formation of the
1107 structural lineaments resulting from the uplift of the Canary Islands Volcanic Province.

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